

Final report

Awareness for stable ecosystems – piloting a cooperative approach in Czechia

AZ 37065

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Zusammenfassung

Landwirtschaftliche Flächen machen 53 % der Gesamtfläche der Tschechischen Republik aus. Daher ist die Landwirtschaft die wichtigste Triebkraft für die Landschaftsveränderungen in der Tschechischen Republik. Dennoch erlebte die Landschaft den dramatischsten Wandel in der sozialistischen Zeit. Die Agrarlandschaft wurde als Produktionsfläche betrachtet und den Anforderungen der schweren Mechanisierung untergeordnet. Infolgedessen verzehnfachte sich die Größe der Ackerflächen, stabilisierende Elemente wurden entfernt und Feuchtgebiete trockengelegt. Diese Veränderungen führten zur Entwicklung der Wind- und Bodenerosion und zum Verlust der biologischen Vielfalt. Heutzutage ist es notwendig, den landwirtschaftlichen Praktiken besondere Aufmerksamkeit zu widmen und praktische Schritte zu unternehmen, um das Landschaftsmosaik im Sinne einer nachhaltigen Entwicklung zu verbessern und den Klimawandel abzuschwächen.

In diesem Projekt haben wir einen Raum für gemeinsame Diskussionen zwischen den lokalen Gemeinden, Landbesitzern, Landwirten, Imkervereinen und Naturschützern geschaffen, um einen gemeinsamen Weg für eine vielfältigere und stabilere Agrarlandschaft zu finden. Um dieses Ziel zu erreichen, haben wir uns entsprechende Ziele gesetzt: Das Hauptziel des Projekts war, das Bewusstsein für stabile Ökosysteme zu schärfen und zu zeigen, was in Agrarlandschaften getan werden kann, um die Widerstandsfähigkeit von Ökosystemen zu verbessern. Die tschechischen Projektpartner entwickelten Publikationen und organisierten Treffen und Exkursionen, um wissenschaftlich fundiertes Wissen über dieses Thema zu verbreiten. Die Anpflanzung von Landschaftselementen auf Grundstücken im Besitz von Gemeinden, um dem Verlust der biologischen Vielfalt entgegenzuwirken, hat das Potenzial, die Zusammenarbeit zwischen den relevanten Akteuren bei Pflanzaktionen und deren Nachsorge zu verbessern. Um die Strukturen und Prozesse der Zusammenarbeit zwischen Landwirten, Kommunen und Naturschützern weiter zu verbessern, wurden in den Modellregionen Modelle der Zusammenarbeit erprobt, die den deutschen Landschaftspflegeverbänden (LPV) ähneln. Diese Zusammenarbeit hat aufgrund des mangelnden Vertrauens und der Missverständnisse über Ökologie in der tschechischen Gesellschaft im Allgemeinen einen innovativen Charakter.

Die im Rahmen des Projekts gewonnenen Erkenntnisse könnten weiterentwickelt und auf weitere tschechische Regionen übertragen werden, insbesondere in Gebieten mit akzeptablen sozialen Bedingungen (z. B. ausreichendes Vertrauen zwischen Landwirten und der staatlichen Verwaltung).

Um die Projektziele zu erreichen, haben wir Maßnahmen wie die Einrichtung von runden Tischen in den Zielgebieten ergriffen, an denen verschiedene Interessengruppen zusammenkommen, um die Hauptprobleme zu ermitteln und die Anpflanzung von Landschaftselementen an einem geeigneten Ort zu planen. Obwohl das primäre Ziel des Projekts nicht direkt die Schaffung von Landschaftselementen war, sondern eher der Aufbau einer Kooperationsstruktur, fanden während der Projektlaufzeit in beiden Projektgebieten Pflanzaktionen statt. So fand im April 2022 in Božice (Region Südmähren) eine Alleepflanzung in Zusammenarbeit mit der örtlichen Landwirtschaftsfamilie, der Gemeinde Božice, einer NRO und Freiwilligen aus dem Dorf statt. Im selben Monat fand eine weitere Pflanzaktion in Lubno (Region Hradec Králové) statt, wo die örtlichen Wildhüter mit Hilfe einer Grundschule aus der Nachbarstadt Nechanice 140 Bäume verschiedener Arten pflanzten.

Im Rahmen dieses Kooperationsmodells wurde durch temporäre Strukturen wie runde Tische, Exkursionen, Seminare und andere Veranstaltungen das Bewusstsein für die Widerstandsfähigkeit von Ökosystemen in der Ackerlandschaft geschärft. Dank dieser Aktivitäten wissen die angesprochenen Akteure nun, welche landwirtschaftlichen und naturschutzfachlichen Praktiken natürlichen Ökosystemen helfen oder schaden können und wie die Landschaftsfunktionen wiederhergestellt werden können.

1 Summary

Agricultural land represents 53% of the total area of the Czech Republic. Therefore, agriculture is the primary driver of landscape changes in the Czech Republic. Nevertheless, the landscape underwent the most dramatic change in the socialist period. The agricultural landscape was considered a productive area and subordinated to the requirements of heavy mechanisation. As a result, the size of arable land plots had increased 10x, stabilising elements were removed, and wetlands were drained. These changes led to the development of wind and soil erosion and biodiversity loss. Nowadays, it is necessary to devote special attention to agricultural practices and make practical steps to improve landscape mosaics towards sustainable development and mitigate climate change.

In this project, we created a space for mutual discussion between the local municipalities, landowners, farmers, beekeepers clubs and conservationists to find a common way for a more diverse and stable agricultural landscape. To achieve this goal, we set relevant objectives: The project's main objective was to raise awareness for stable ecosystems and what can be done in agricultural landscapes to improve ecosystem resilience. The Czech project partners developed publications and organised meetings and excursions to spread science-based knowledge about this topic. Plant landscape features on plots owned by communes to counter the loss of biodiversity have the potential to improve cooperation between relevant stakeholders during planting events and its aftercare. To enhance further structures and processes of cooperation between farmers, communes and nature conservationists, models of collaboration similar to German Landcare Associations (LPVs) were tested in the model regions. This cooperation has an innovative character due to the lack of trust and the misunderstandings about ecology in Czech society in general.

The knowledge gained from the project could be further developed and transferred to Czech regions, especially in areas with acceptable social conditions (e.g., trust between farmers and the state administration is sufficient).

To reach the project's objectives, we implemented measures such as establishing round tables in the target areas for meeting different interest groups to identify the main problems and plan to create landscape features in a suitable place. Even though the primary intention of the project was not directly the creation of landscape features but rather the establishment of a cooperation structure, during the duration of the project, plantings events took place in both project areas. For example, in April 2022, one alley planting took place in Božice (Southern Moravia region) in cooperation with the local family farmer, Božice municipality, NGO and volunteers from the village. The same month another planting event took place in Lubno (Hradec Králové region), where the local gamekeepers, with the help of an elementary school from a neighbouring Nechanice town planted 140 trees of different species.

In this cooperation model, through temporary structures of round tables, excursions, seminars and other events, we raise awareness of ecosystem resilience in the arable landscape. Thanks to these activities, now the addressed stakeholders know the farming and conservation practices that can help or damage natural ecosystems and how to restore landscape functions.

2 Project activities

2.1. Development of guidelines

At the beginning of the project CSO and Ekotoxa created a template for the meetings with stakeholders. Notes from individual meetings were systematically gathered into the template with focus on

- the overall impression from each meeting,
- possibilities of development of cooperation,
- identification of the main problems from stakeholders' perception and
- next steps for future cooperation.

This documentation serves a basis for sharing our experience from the project. Although there are already several methodologies in the Czech environment focused on the cooperation between various stakeholders, most of them do not deal directly with the problem of a healthy landscape or, on the contrary, are devoted to the creation of landscape elements, but neglect the importance of mutual cooperation.

Ekotoxa has now published a methodology of initiating a cooperation for adaptations to climate change on the landscape level among local stakeholders (mayors, farmers, landowners, nature conservationists) based on the experience from a project Ekotoxa worked on between January 2019 and June 2022 (Lada - project for Technology Agency of the Czech Republic¹). The key focus in the methodology is on preparation and organisation of a workshop for stakeholders of one municipality in order to jointly propose local adaptation measures.

Since the methodology is now available online in a form of a pdf, and since we are currently proposing a follow up of this pilot project, we decided not to publish another pdf of guidelines. The experience gained during the pilot project will be shared through a series of short articles on project websites of CSO and Ekotoxa and other websites read by key groups of stakeholders. We will also introduce our experience in an online seminar for LAG, conservationists, the public interested in nature conservation and colleagues from Ekotoxa and CSO will be also invited to raise their awareness about this topic.

2.2. Analysis of key actors: existing stakeholders in pilot regions and assessing the level of existing trust

Pilot region Southern Moravia

As a pilot region, Ekotoxa supports in Southern Moravia the area of MAS Hrušovansko (Local Action Group, LAG) regarding the size of the area and existing structure (LAG).

The LAG Hrušovansko is in the Southern Moravian Region on the border with Austria between Znojmo and Mikulov. It consists of twelve municipalities that belong to the district of Znojmo and one to the district of Břeclav. This rural region is characterized by a flat to slightly undulating landscape dotted with fields and vineyards.

¹ https://starfos.tacr.cz/en/project/TL02000431?query_code=qhkiaacbifwa#project-main. The activities in the Lada project and the DBU project this report refers to were strictly separated, only connections were drawn and experiences shared.

Figure 1 Map of the microregion Southern Moravia (Ekotoxa)

In the region, there are 13 villages, around 20 large agriculture subjects and more than 30 mid-size and small subjects including family farms with many vineyards, and no organization purely focused on nature conservation. Organisations representing nature conservation are located near regional and district cities, including state authorities (Nature Conservation Agency of the Czech Republic (NCA CR), PLA Authorities, nature conservation departments of Southern Moravia regional office) and NGOs (regional branch of CSO, Nadace Partnerství, Větvení and other, see chapters 2.3, 2.4, 2.5).

Pilot region Hradec Králové

In the pilot region supported by CSO, there are 20 rural municipalities, six main agriculture cooperatives, several private farmers, and no organisation purely focused on nature conservation. Agricultural cooperatives are often the largest employers here. The difference in the size of municipalities in the region is considerable. The largest town in a microregion is Nechanice with 2 349 inhabitants, whereas the smallest village Pšánky has only 73 people. The microregion is geographically specific in that it is located in the hinterland of the regional city of Hradec Králové. Thanks to this location, a large part of the territory belong to the Hradec Králové agglomeration.

Figure 2 Map of Nechanicko microregion (CSO)

A number of associations, clubs, associations, and non-profit organisations have been active for a long time in the region's municipalities, which usually participate in the organisation of cultural and social events in the villages. Local authorities support these activities partially financially and usually provide material facilities and equipment. Volunteer firefighters, sports clubs, gamekeeper clubs, senior clubs and gardening clubs run their activities in almost every village.

The activities of the associations are mainly focused on adults. Interest activities for children are usually realised in cooperation with elementary schools, but the region suffers from a lack of qualified lecturers. This microregion is also operated by LAG Hradecký venkov o.p.s. with the main purpose of connecting municipalities, companies, the public and NGOs for local development.

To a certain point, nature conservation is carried out by local gamekeeper groups and some beekeepers that are active almost in each village. Gamekeepers usually play a significant role in wildlife and landscape management, and some groups are even engaged in creating landscape features such as planting woody plants. Some of the local hunting groups could be perceived as local landscape conservation groups. The hunting association from Nechanice has started cooperation with CSO already before this project.

2.2.1. Economic variables

The typical conflict between nature conservation and farmers is usually driven by incentives coming from improperly set conditions of agriculture subsidies within the Common agriculture policy (CAP) that indirectly motivates farmers to eliminate all landscape features on their land, including plantings created through regional projects. This might happen even on the land that is rented by farmers from the local administration.

The size of the villages affects the level of involvement in the project. Firstly, it is problematic to meet with mayors from the smallest villages and actively engage them in the project because they are often fully employed elsewhere. However, when we succeeded in meeting them, they welcomed the project positively and provided us with information. They still did not promise to invest more energy to carry out further actions as they simply did not have time for it. Secondly, the smallest villages are not motivated to participate much due to their low budget. For example, the smallest village in the pilot region Hradec Kralove has an annual budget of 47,265 EUR.

Common argument across the regions against creating landscape features concerns the lack of money for follow-up maintenance. However, the solution may be the involvement of local associations or schools, who can provide maintenance of newly created landscape features through volunteer activities.

2.2.2. Social factors

Both pilot regions

The level of involvement depends on the attitude of the mayor and local people. In some villages, we witnessed exemplary teamwork and independence in landscape restoration efforts. In other villages, mayors do not have the energy and motivation to negotiate with stakeholders.

Gamekeepers and beekeepers mentioned that their associations are facing a steep decline in tradition and a lack of young people involved.

Farmers from the region also often mention a shortage of workers caused by the young generation's lack of interest in farming and hard work.

Large and conventional farmers are complaining about the media and the picture that is created about conventional farming. The public perceives large farmers as destroyers of nature and biodiversity, which is not necessarily the truth in every case.

Farmers who joined the project had already started adapting their businesses to include non-productive functions. They were open to new ideas and collaboration and also stayed in touch with the project team. On the other hand, most of the farmers we attempted to engage declined our invitations. Usually, they argued they were too busy, already had advisors, or their main priority was to survive economically. Other possible reasons we identified in a previous qualitative study (Meierová and Chvátalová, 2022) are that they were exhausted from various barriers to their perceived main role - producing food, frustrated, and resigned to even make mental space for considering any engagement.

Gamekeepers generally do not welcome the idea of renewing historical pathways because they attract people, dog walkers, and motor vehicles, which threaten wildlife. Gamekeepers prefer landscape features that serve only for wildlife and are inaccessible for people (e.g., an element placed in the middle of a field).

Most of the people who got involved in the pilot project belong to the older generation, and their general attitude towards the project was often conservative.

Pilot region Southern Moravia

The LAG Hrušovansko does not seem very active. In the recently finished seven-year strategic period, no subject applied for a subsidy on a project in the landscape through the LAG. The LAG meets only a few times a year, but the mayors communicate regularly, discuss and inspire each other.

Some farmers and many other stakeholders complain that landowners are interested only in the amount of money for the leased land and not in soil and land quality. In addition, a significant part of the owners are descendants living in other parts of the Czech Republic and don't have a relationship with the land.

The region is located in the area from where a significant part of (mainly German) inhabitants was displaced after WW2 and where people from other parts of former Czechoslovakia moved to. Therefore, the relationship with the land was broken and has not been fully established yet. There is also a low level of trust among people in this area. Moreover, even one mayor worried about the cooperation with a German organisation.

There is low trust of farmers towards environmentalists. Farmers are more open to advice from other farmers rather than from experts who are perceived as not understanding their needs. They are also often too busy and do not have the mental space for thinking about non-productive functions or creating a vision of their farm or enterprise.

Mayors and farmers from the microregion also often complained that they lack a workforce since local people would rather take better-paid jobs near Austria's border.

In some cases, communication among stakeholders is blocked by long-term conflicts. We also encountered entangled local power relationships, which hinder efforts for clear communication and cooperation. The most severe case was a power relationship between a large agricultural holding and local farmers and landowners who depend on it to buy inputs and sell outputs.

Pilot region Hradec Kralove

During the year, LAG Hradecký venkov organises some events for the public within the microregion. Most of them are dedicated to supporting people at risk of social exclusion. LAG Hradecký venkov has the community-led local development strategy for 2021-2027. As part of the strategic goal focused on the environment, there is support for the landscape's ecological stability, including biodiversity and protection of natural elements through land consolidation and revitalisation of water bodies and watercourses or planting and maintaining greenery.

In 2021 LAG had 47 partners from the public, private, non-profit and business sectors. Some of these partners applied for a subsidy from EU funds. In the previous project period (2014 – 2020), LAG Hradecký venkov managed to implement projects within Integrated Regional Operational Programme (IROP) - 20 projects, Rural Development Programme (RDP) - 26 projects, including greening projects and project for support forest recreational function, the Operational Programme Environment (OPE) - tree projects focused on residential greenery in the intravilan of the municipality and four project and Operational Programme Employment (OPE). LAG representatives are also willing to share our invitations for events that we organise in the microregion.

Smaller farmers often have to deal with lower competitiveness as compared to large agricultural companies. Their fields are affected by frequent weather fluctuations, which cause extended periods of drought and heavy rainfall in a short time. The landscape has a significant problem with short-term water retention, mainly due to past drainage and destruction of landscape features. Given that three-quarters of Czech farmers lease their land from the owners, they farm it in such a way that its production potential continues to decrease. It is important to mention that approximately 70% of the land is owned by a few large agricultural companies, compared to Austria, where agricultural land is managed almost exclusively by small family farms. The rural population is ageing, and farmers have trouble finding successors to take over their work. CSO often met with the opinion that local landowners are merely interested in their land's economic value and in building new houses. A significant part of the owners are descendants living

in other parts of the Czech Republic and these no longer have the binding to the land as their previous generations had. Only about 5% of farmers in the Czech Republic are under the age of 35. The amount of wages for workers in agriculture, low prestige and at the same time, hard work is why many young people are not interested in farming.

Nechanicko microregion is one of the sought-after locations for individual housing construction. Above all, municipalities near the city of Hradec Králové and municipalities with good transport connections to the regional capital are increasingly becoming sought after for population migration to the countryside. However, many municipalities are unprepared for such an influx of new residents. The problem with suburbanisation processes was mentioned during the interviews with mayors and citizens. Many roads are in poor technical condition. Accessibility of social services for the elderly, doctors, shops and other civic amenities in smaller municipalities is unsatisfactory. Many newly immigrated citizens are not interested in what is happening in the village, are not involved in decision-making processes, and do not participate in social life. Many new immigrants use Hradec Králové for cultural and relaxation purposes.

2.2.3. Natural variables

Pilot region Southern Moravia

The region lies in a warm to a very warm climate. The average annual temperature reaches 9 - 10 °C, which is above average compared to the whole Czech Republic. The Hrušovany region lies in the rain shadow of the Bohemian-Moravian Highlands. Therefore, the annual total precipitation reaches only 450 - 500 mm per year. Most of the area is covered by black earth - clayey and loamy. The earth is flat here with a maximum slope of 3 degrees. The land is used as arable for growing corn, wine, vegetables and sugar beets, grain, rapeseed and sunflower. There are also floodplains in the Hrušovany region, which have a high groundwater level and are thus permanently wet and are used only as meadows (especially in the vicinity of the Litobratřický brook). The area is dominated by the rivers Dyje and Jevišovka. But there are also a number of smaller streams and irrigation canals.

Overall, there is a lack of water in the landscape in the LAG Hrušovany. The area is one of the driest places in the Czech Republic. The whole area is also facing deteriorating air quality, the indicators for the protection of health and the ecosystem have been exceeded.

Hrušovansko is located between the Podyjí National Park and the Pálava Protected Landscape Area, there are several small specially protected areas. In addition, there are ten small-scale conservation areas protecting ponds, swamps, river Jevišovka and neighbouring areas, including forests.

Figure 3 Typical landscape with large flat fields without landscape features in Southern Moravia (V. Chvátalová)

In one village and a few villages neighbouring with the pilot region, there are localities with a former occurrence of *Otis tarda*, which are part of a proposed rescue program of this bird (not authorised yet by the government). Therefore, the activities in the landscape are prioritised to support the return of this bird, i.e. some measures regarded necessary in this open landscape as a planting of windbreaks, alleys and sole trees should be prohibited according to the proposed rescue program.

Figure 4 Intensive agricultural production is typical for Southern Moravia, here watering corn (V. Chvátalová)

Czech System of Ecological Stability projects a net of biocorridors and biocentres across the country to support connectivity between “biodiversity islands” for wildlife. Project proposals on a local, regional and supraregional level are included in the strategic plans of each municipality. However, the degree of their realisation in this region is deficient.

Pilot region Hradec Kralove

The project region Nechanicko is located in the area of rolling land between forests. Most of the landscape is affected by intensive agricultural production. Oilseed rape, peas, poppies, winter wheat, sugar beet, corn and spring barley are currently grown here. According to the Quitt climate classification, the microregion lies in a warm climate area with an average annual temperature of 9.29 °C (measured between 2001–2010), and precipitation during this period was 593.4 mm. The area is characterised by long, warm and dry summers and short, moderately warm and dry winters.

This area belongs to the geomorphological district Nechanická tabule, which is made up of calcareous claystone and siltstone rocks. The soil-forming substrate of the monitored area is gravel-sand with a subsoil of saliva.

The river Bystřice flows around Nechanice and forms a vast floodplain. In the spring, the Bystřice flows into the meadows in the northeast direction from the city centre to the area where the water fortress used to be. Water reservoirs were created by waterlogging local lakes; some of them, such as the pond in Komárov, are used today for fishing. The region was heavily waterlogged in the past, which was solved at the end of the 19th century with drainage works. The monitored area was part of an early modern pond system. Ponds were also built on the Bystřica river. This system was abolished during the 19th century, when ponds dried up, and changed to fields or meadows. Currently, the agricultural landscape suffers from severe droughts during the growing season here.

Figure 5 Sparse vegetation in Nechanicko microregion (V. Zámečnick)

There are several protected areas with different levels of protection in the microregion. Here we can find two Nature 2000 reserves: Bystřice and Nechanice - Lodín. In addition, three natural monuments and several memorial trees, mainly old oaks, are registered here.

Along the Bystřice watercourse, there is a Special Area of Conservation (SAC) called Bystřice, where the main object of protection is the thick shelled river mussel (*Unio crassus*). The modifications of the watercourse bed, bank stabilisation and the construction of levees to prevent the migration of fishes had a negative effect on the occurrence of the thick shelled river mussel. Agriculture is a significant factor causing the introduction of muddy sediments and other pollutants into the watercourse. In 2010, a survey of the aquatic malacofauna was carried out and a total of 21 species of aquatic molluscs were found. Three of them were endangered species. Near to the SAC, two specially protected plant species in the severely threatened species category (*Allium angulosum* and *Teucrium scordium*), were found, and the occurrence of the critically endangered European crayfish (*Astacus astacus*) was also confirmed here. Larvae of the hermit beetle (*Osmoderma barnabita*) were found in the municipality of Dohalice and Mokrovousy. Individuals of the common kingfisher (*Alcedo atthis*) were observed in Kratonohy.

Nechanice - Lodín is SAC which belongs to a protected area of the Natura 2000 system. The main objective of protection is mixed forest stands in the middle of an agricultural landscape. *Melica picta*, common cowslip (*Primula veris*) or martagon lily (*Lilium martagon*) can be found here.

In the cadastres of individual municipalities, the territorial system of environmental stability (TSES) at the regional and local levels (regional and local biocorridors and biocentres) are defined. However, according to the mayors, the TSES is inefficient and difficult to implement.

The microregion falls into protected heritage areas of the National Heritage Institute, because of the decisive battle of the Prussia-Austrian War in 1866, on July 3rd. Nechanice, one of the three places where the battle started, was attacked by the Prussian Elbe Army.

2.2.4. Information from wider society

Gamekeepers are often excluded from the essential discussions about landscape and conservation. It is known that land owners can blackmail farmers who receive subsidies for non-productive elements and require a share of the income. The Czech System of Ecological Stability is not always designed in an

effective way. Often the plans and concepts do not consider the ownership of land which makes the proposed project impossible to implement.

Land consolidation is a very lengthy process, and the quality differs within the Czech Republic. In some villages, the consolidations are really well designed. In other municipalities, for example, large blocks of arable land remain and would be worth dividing (still remaining the risk of large soil erosion). Other specific proposals for measures include, for example, proposals for access roads to land involving asphalt roads instead of natural ones.

2.3. Meetings with farmers, nature conservationists and mayors to start cooperation and raise awareness

Pilot region Southern Moravia

Ekotoxa has built a database of contacts including mayors, farmers, landowners, gamekeepers, local organisations, nature conservationists and the public.

Ekotoxa staff has established contact with all the thirteen **mayors** of the microregion. We individually met 11 mayors and made repeated telephone interviews with two other mayors. Since the first personal contact, we have further communicated via phone or email and with some of the mayors met at the round tables and seminar. We also repeatedly met two former mayors, one of them with education and experience in landscape planning and urban development.

We have approached 50 **subjects who farm** in the microregion via email or telephone. Although we aimed to make at least short telephone interviews, many farmers declined the call too soon. Finally, it was possible to gain insights from and explain the benefits of the project to four farmers on the phone and four others at personal meetings. Additionally, 10 other farmers joined round tables.

We have contacted 25 **nature conservationists** from state authorities (Nature Conservation Agency of the Czech Republic (NCA CR), PLA Authorities, nature conservation departments of Southern Moravia regional office) and NGOs. Longer telephone interviews were made with four of them who later also joined the round tables. We are in contact with five other conservationists who were approached by telephone or email for consultations.

Five **gamekeeper associations** were contacted and subsequently, we met with five representatives of three associations, first at individual meetings and later at the roundtables.

We also approached approximately 15 **local people** who we met during the visits to the microregion. The consultant also personally met and further cooperated by telephone and email with a project manager of the **LAG Hrušovansko**.

Figure 6 Example of a map as base for the personal communication with stakeholders, here from the microregion Southern Moravia

Four **local organisations** interested in nature and/or cultural activities were contacted. However, only one organisation started to cooperate with us. Others were either not interested, too busy with their own agenda or turned out defunct.

Each meeting was preceded by the studying of documents and preparing a map based on the Spatial Landscape Study created in 2018 by Ekotoxa for Znojmo, a municipality with extended powers, which also covers the area of the region. The meetings were connected to the mapping of the terrain and asking local people on the way about their perception of the landscape and introducing the project.

During the meetings, the consultant not only presented, but listened to the needs of the stakeholders, investigated which proposals for landscape measures were acceptable or appreciated and what was the reason for that, and which other problems they perceived. Furthermore, the consultant always explained the aim of the project and invited the following activities such as the round table meetings and the seminar of DVL.

Apart from individual meetings, Ekotoxa has organised a meeting with a family farmer and gamekeepers from one village, a member of the local branch of Czech ornithology society and a farmer specialised on the protection of landscape in a different region.

Pilot region Hradec Kralove

Unlike in the pilot region Southern Moravia, Václav Zámečník is living directly in Nechanice, the heart of the pilot region, and for the last 12 years he is actively protecting farmland birds, especially nests of Lapwings. Through this work, he met several farmers and these personal contacts and knowledge of the environment helped to start the project. Also, from 2018 as a member of the council of Nechanice had a chance to push together with local hunters for the restoration of the ploughed former field roads to become new landscape features - grassy strips with bushes and trees. As a result, a new landscape feature was planted in April 2022 near village Lubno with active participation of the CSO.

CSO builds a database of contacts, including mayors, farmers, gamekeepers, local organisations, landowners and public and other stakeholder groups (beekeepers, fishermen and local businesses). In total CSO gathered **more than 130 contacts**. We have tried to reach approximately 50 of them that we have considered being key for the project. The rest of the contacts were either not considered to be a priority or were gathered during project activities and there was no time to meet them yet.

Since the beginning of the project, CSO has undergone **more than 38 individual meetings**. Most of the meetings were with **mayors and other members of municipality boards (14)**, followed by farmers (8), people working in nature conservation (5), gamekeepers and fishermen (5), local organisations (3), and inhabitants of the regions (3). Some of the people are representatives of more than one group – e.g. one of the mayors is a director of an agricultural cooperative and a gamekeeper at the same time. Also, some of the people we have met more than once.

Firstly CSO contacted the mayor of Mokrovousy village Mrs. Jana Pečenková, who is also deputy chair of **the association of municipalities called Microregion Nechanicko**. In the past, she was the main engine that through Microregion Nechanicko has organised some actions in the farmland such as planting of the trees along field roads and even some division of large fields by grassy strips with tree plantation, so the establishment of cooperation was logically offered. Furthermore, this valuable partner is helping us to communicate project activities by inviting mayors to the seminar, promoting our project and by publishing articles in the local press.

Each meeting was preceded by studying documents and the preparation of presentations for each municipality. CSO built a database of proposed landscape features in the region, including ideas that emerged during the meetings and project proposals from individual strategic plans. The database currently includes 130 landscape features.

As a result of our meeting with **Mrs. Dagmar Smetiprachová, mayor of village Stěžery**, CSO has been invited to a council meeting on 1.9.2021 with the participation of landscape designers working on Complex landscaping, local farmers and the public. During the meeting, a project was introduced by V. Zámečník and afterwards potential new green infrastructure of the village was discussed with the participants.

Mrs. Smetiprachova also invited CSO for a public hearing on 7.10.2021 in Stěžery concerning the revitalisation of a small plot of woody vegetation that was widely rejected by the public and local mayor. The aim of this revitalization is to abolish the grove, cover it with waste (soil and stones) and build houses with associated planting of native tree species and sowing with grass. CSO participated in the negotiation with our bird data from the locality gathered during spring 2021. Investors and developers will probably win the case, but at least CSO built trust with the mayor and local people.

Altogether, there are **more than 80 farmers** working in the microregion. Six of them are big companies working on large areas of more than 1000 ha. Within the project, we have contacted all of those at least by phone and with **five of them we had met in person**. Another **14 usually family farmers** were reached at least by phone, and **three of them by personal meetings**. Meetings with farmers were focused on the condition of the farmland and possibilities to improve its quality through agriculture subsidies. They were

also consulted on specific proposals regarding the fields they farm on, with the aim of ascertaining their position.

Among other stakeholders active in the farmland belong **hunters, fishermen or bee-keepers**. Again, a lot of people pursue all these hobbies at once. We spoke with members of three hunter clubs that manage the majority of microregion land. In particular, hunters from club Lověna Nechanice have been active in recent years in greening of the farmland. Also, we have met with the chairman of the fishing district Mr. Milan Vlč.

We decided to meet also **with the public** with some knowledge or activities of the Nechanice countryside. Especially meeting the 93-year-old historian Václav Pražák was very unique. As an author, he has published two books about Nechanice and the surrounding countryside that are locally well known.

Meetings with **organisations active in nature protection** took place after the round tables. Experts from Eastern Bohemia were invited to give their opinion to the most promising proposals that came out of the individual meeting and round tables. A positive result of these meetings was the confirmation of the feasibility of the measures. CSO also visited the local office of the expert body of the Ministry of Environment in Pardubice to discuss financial support and its conditions of the proposed intentions.

Overall, the feedback from the first meetings is rather positive, and all stakeholders are willing to cooperate at some level.

2.4. Setting up round tables and other cooperation structures to foster cooperation

Both regions

It was most relevant to set up round tables when all stakeholders were available, i.e. during the off-season of farmers. Also we wanted to meet key stakeholders first in person to introduce our goals in detail and get their private reactions, so logically round tables were planned in the second half of the project.

Pilot region Southern Moravia

Altogether, six round tables took place in four villages.

The consultants of Ekotoxa first organised two subsequent smaller round tables for stakeholders of the microregion village Božice in October 2021 in the frame of the parallel project, during which workshops were held in different places in South Moravia (see chapter 2.1).

The first round table organised in the frame of this project took place in Milovice, a village close to the microregion in December 2021. Since cooperation was already emerging there, we decided to start there to draw inspiration and evaluate the possibility of expanding our pilot region to include this village.

The next round tables took place in the microregion villages Šanov, Čejkovice and Božice between February and March 2022.

The round tables that brought the stakeholders together for the first time were organised only for invited participants. We have invited participants based on the information we gathered about the area from desktop analysis and communication with stakeholders about the state of landscape, interests, needs and powers of stakeholders. The invited stakeholders always included mayors and/or vice mayors of a village, local farmers interested in sustainable practices and non-productive activities, farmers who could share best practice examples (not necessarily from the project microregion), subjects who farmed on field blocks identified as problematic, nature conservationists and chairmen of gamekeeper associations. These stakeholders usually also represented landowners of the local agricultural land.

Figure 7 Two maps of landscape risks and proposals from two round tables in the microregion Southern Moravia

Stakeholders who accepted the invitation and participated are usually represented by all these groups. It was usually difficult to engage farmers from purely productively oriented businesses, although they were the owners and users of land, which would most need change. However, we succeeded in having one representative of such businesses at each round table.

The round tables always took place in the meeting spaces of municipal authorities and lasted approximately three hours. Apart from the organiser from Ekotoxa, an external facilitator took part to

help with creating a safe space for everyone to engage in the discussion and make it constructive. Four to ten participants represented the local interests gathered around the round tables.

The Ekotoxa consultant opened the meetings by presenting the aim of the project and round table. The participants introduced themselves and their expectations of the meeting in the introductory circle. They then expressed problems and risks in the local landscape they perceived and barriers to tackling those issues. That was subsequently completed by a short presentation of the state of the local landscape, projections of climate change impacts, and possible adaptation measures, including examples of best practices and financing possibilities by the consultant of Ekotoxa. After this, participants discussed measures and landscape level adaptations for their village that would be effective and could be practically implemented and were accepted by all the stakeholders. We usually animated this discussion to find out what measures are/are not acceptable, why, how those barriers could be overcome, and how we could help each other with solving these issues. Simultaneously, we recorded the named landscape problems and proposals for solutions in words and maps. The meetings were finished by wrapping the outcomes, tasks and outlook of the next steps. Participants were also encouraged to express their impression of the round table and if their expectations were met.

The round table in Božice, the village where stakeholders had already met twice in a narrower circle described above, was open for the public of the village. Sixteen people joined the meeting, including those who had already attended the preceding meetings and new ones, representing the municipality, farmers, landowners, gamekeepers, nature conservationists and local public. We have further discussed possible landscape adaptations based on past meetings' outcomes and input from newcomers. Together we have planned a planting of a tree alley on the arable land of a local family farmer along a field path in the ownership of the municipality, which was realised in the frame of this project in the beginning of April 2022.

The planning and planting of the alley turned out to be a good example of cooperation toward an ecologically stable landscape. The farmer who proposed the planting promoted it at other meetings as a success of common discussions. The preparations involved the cooperation of the farmer, mayor, vice mayor, former vice mayor and project architect of the planting together with the Ekotoxa consultant and coordination of volunteers from the village and NGO Větvění who helped with the planting.

nr.	name	date	place	number of participants
1	Round table in Božice 1	07.10.2021	Božice	8
2	Round table in Božice 2	25.10.2021	Božice	10
3	Round table in Milovice	08.12.2021	Milovice	8
4	Round table in Šanov	10.02.2022	Šanov	4
5	Round table in Čejkovice	24.02.2022	Čejkovice	6
6	Round table in Božice 3	14.03.2022	Božice	16

Table 1 List of round tables in the Southern Moravian microregion

The outcomes of the round tables were always analysed with the focus on the process itself (interactions among stakeholders), the proposals for landscape adaptations and the obstacles. We have digitalised a map of landscape problems and risks and proposals of adaptations supplemented with a table gathering details about ownership and affected users, the degree of difficulty of the implementation, possible sources of financial support and assigned people who can do anything about it (e.g., municipality or nature conservation body responsible for a particular locality). That served as a basis for the next steps. I.e. we have further contacted affected people and experts to consult the possibility of implementing individual proposals. Participants of the round tables were updated about the development and asked for cooperation when appropriate.

Pilot region Hradec Králové

In microregion Nechanicko we have decided to organise round tables as bigger meetings with directly invited people usually from several villages. For this reason, three key locations were preselected - Nechanice, Stěžery and Mžany. All round tables were prepared the same way - in this preparation we have contacted Ms Marta Kotecká from an organisation called Beleco, that has long-time experience in mediating different types of meetings. Together we have prepared a detailed structure of the round table, including timing and concrete tasks for the participants. The so-called “feeling map” was chosen as the main tool of communication, in which participants in groups added places they like or dislike and places where they see some potential for change. Results of the working group were then presented to the rest of the participants. All round tables took place in the municipality areas as a result of cooperation with mayors and without need to pay for the rent. All key stakeholders were invited (mayors, members of municipality boards, hunters, fishers, beekeepers, public with a deeper interest in nature protection).

Dates and number of participants of the round tables:

27.1.2022 Nechanice - 18 participants

3.2. Stěžery - 17 participants

17.3. Mžany - 14 participants

All round tables have brought some ideas, how to improve the quality of the farmland. After round tables all maps were put in GIS systems and for each round table a map summarising all comments from participants was prepared. All ideas were collected with a focus on the most beneficial one. All participants also received an overall evaluation of the round table by email.

Figure 8 Emotional map used during round tables (CSO)

The most promising proposals were selected, and we continued to work with them. If proposals were directly connected with farmland, we have discussed them with concerned farmers to see their

willingness to accept potential changes within farming. Selected proposals were also presented to competent state authorities (AOPK - the expert body of the MoE). Consultation with them was focused on their acceptance of the proposal from the state nature body view and especially potential financial support from financial instruments of the MoE. This way, we find out that two of the most ambitious proposals could be fully compensated from structural funds. Also, necessary administrative steps before realisation of the proposals were discussed. Subsequently, we invited several experts from nature conservation fields to show them the most relevant project sites (David Číp from the local environmental NGO JARO, Roman Rozínek - expert on wetland revitalization and amphibians from private company called NaturaServis, entomologist and botanist from NGO Pestré Polabí) to discuss with them possibilities of the site development and their suggestions. In addition, the expert on water management responsible for the local river network met with us to give us their technical view and overall view on the intentions. As a result, a plan for the revitalisation of the wetland in Komárov (part of Nechanice) was prepared by Roman Rozínek.

Also along with round tables, other events for public tagging farmland bird protection were organised. Twice we met with the public with interest in nature protection to search for the nests of Lapwing, which otherwise would be destroyed by agricultural machinery:

29.4.2022 - 3 people, 1 nest found

1.5.2022 - 6 people, 3 nests found

Birds were also presented at the event for the public, again organised in cooperation with Nechanice municipality. The event took place on 2.6.2022 with the participation of 16 people.

2.5. Networking

Both pilot regions

Nadace Partnerství (“Environmental Foundation”) - Ekotoxa and CSO have developed a grant database which serves as a financial advisor for everyone together with this NGO. It went online on the website run by Nadace Partnerství at the beginning of February 2022. The website Živá půda (“Living land”) guides people interested in helping nature through a number of measures and related financial measures. The database is being expanded to include additional grant titles. It includes subsidies from the Ministry of Agriculture, the Ministry of the Environment and European subsidies such as the Agri-Environment Climate Scheme. This cooperation aims to ease the bureaucratic language of websites and documents and to provide clear information about subsidies programs. This activity contributed to one of our objectives to create a financial leaflet (see PR activities) and has an impact beyond the project (we aim to further develop, expand and promote the database nationwide in the proposed follow-up project). The cooperation in the development of the grant database with the project partners in the frame of this project and DBU as a donor are mentioned on the website of the NGO.

Friends of the Earth Czech Republic - this NGO is getting more active in agriculture landscape conservation and is currently proposing regional projects in the Czech Republic similar to ours. We have been consulting issues about CAP and sharing experience with agriculture experts. Thanks to our knowledge of the initiation of cooperation among diverse stakeholders for stable ecosystems, the NGO approached us to become partners in a project they planned. The project gained support and started in June 2022, intending to promote cooperation on a regional level to develop the sectors of organic farming, processing, and consumption. Friends of the Earth Czech Republic supports ecological agriculture, which ensures a varied landscape, water retention, decent conditions for animals and space for nature. It also supports the production of local food, produced without the use of pesticides. They have created a [directory of farmers](#), so people can find the farmers closest to where they live. Friends of the Earth International is part of a strong food sovereignty movement, which includes The International

Planning Committee for Food Sovereignty (IPC) and the Civil Society and Indigenous Peoples' Mechanism for relations with the UN Committee on World Food Security.

Biodiversity working group - Václav Zámečník from CSO consults CAP issues within a Biodiversity working group negotiating the national plan of CAP. Thanks to the partnership, Ekotoxa could also contribute with the experience made in Hrušovansko microregion. Furthermore, the discussions with stakeholders during this project brought relevant insights, which we transferred with the aim to tailor the national CAP plan to reflect nature conservation and farmers' needs better.

Association of private farmers – we have reached to the association for contacts with their members in the pilot regions. Unfortunately, there is only one farmer who is a member of this association, which promotes non-productive functions of farming in the Hrušovansko microregion. However, the chairman of the regional branch of the association participated at one round table in Hrušovansko in the role of a farmer sharing best practice experience. We keep in touch and the association agreed to share information about our activities in the proposed project aimed at spreading the experience of cooperation nationwide.

Project Coalition for Healthy Landscape: enforcement of systemic transformation to increase the Czech landscape's resilience to the impacts of climate change - CSO work together with Environmental Foundation and Friends of the Earth Czech Republic on a project whose main goals are to promote changes in official policies and legislators, landowners' empowerment to use a full range of their property law, and to initiate society-wide debate on problems and ways of solving the state of the Czech landscape and pressing the issue of the right to a healthy environment for Czech citizens.

Pilot region Southern Moravia

Figure 9 Alley planting with volunteers in the microregion Southern Moravia (V. Chvátalová)

The consultant presented the project at various formal and informal events and raised awareness about the necessity to support cooperation (incl. the example of LPVs) among various stakeholders for a fertile and biodiverse landscape; these include events attended among others by politicians: the Final conference of the parallel project (see chapter 2.1), Sympóziem Živého zemědělství (“Symposium der lebenden Landwirtschaft”); and e.g. screening with a discussion of a documentary Krajina v tísní (“Landscape in need”) and of an environmental short film “Global Water Dances”.

We have also contacted various NGOs supporting landscape feature implementation and recorded their interest in sharing knowledge about cooperation among diverse stakeholders. Furthermore, after attending a round table, a director of a local elementary school suggested cooperation among their school and local farmers with our support.

Pilot region Hradec Kralove

At events organised by CSO within the microregion, representatives from LPV, local mayors and other stakeholders offered cooperation in implementing the project and shared their experiences. We also cooperated with two external ornithologists who created a farmland bird survey in the region and provided the project team with data.

Figure 10 Public lecture about avifauna of Nechanicko (CSO, M. Kadavá)

Ptáci Nechanicka

2. 6. 2022

v zasedací místnosti Městského úřadu
Husovo nám. 83, Nechanice

18:00-19:30
povídání o ptácích
Nechanicka doplněné
fotoprojekcí

20:00-22:00
posezení u piva u Josefa
Sopky (Kulturní dům v
Nechanicích)

22:00-23:00
noční výprava?

Kontakt:
Václav Zámečník
zamecnik@birdlife.cz
+420 776 368 360

Figure 11 Invitation to seminar Birds of Nechanicko

Mayor Pečenková from the Mokrovousy municipality and, at the same time, a member of The confederation of municipalities Nechanicko microregion, allow us to inform local residents about the current development of the project and upcoming events through articles in the local Nechanicko Newsletter.

To create landscape features, we contacted non-profit organisations operating in the microregion to consult with them about our plans. As part of the internal meeting, there was a mutual introduction of the organisations and our project with the Pestré Polabí organisation. Their goal is dedicated to the protection of ecologically valuable biotopes in the Polabí area. This organisation has been officially operating as a nature conservation association for about a year and is composed mainly of young people interested in nature conservation near their residences. This means they protect places that they know well and at the same time have often formed a relationship with since childhood. The representatives have promised that they will speak at some of the events organised in the future to encourage the young people's interest in forming their own associations along the lines of LPV.

Figure 12 Alley planting in Lubno by local schoolchildren and gamekeepers (CSO, M. Kadava)

We also met with the chairman of the action conservation group JARO which today consists of several basic organisations of the Czech Union for Nature Conservation. JARO is involved in nature conservation through various activities and is currently one of the most active citizens' associations for practical nature conservation in the Czech Republic, which takes care of dozens of protected areas.

The following list shows all of the meetings in the microregion

Name	Surname	Position/affiliation	Municipality	Date of meeting *
Jana	Pečenková	mayor, deputy chairman of Microregion Nechanicko	Mokrovousy	3/17/2021
Věra	Macháčková	mayor	Boharyně	5/7/2021
Josef	Hošek	hunter, Lověna Nechanice	Nechanice	5/7/2021
Luděk	Homoláč	mayor, director of agriculture company, hunter	Stračov	5/21/2021
Petr	Švasta	mayor	Dolní Přím	5/27/2021

Dagmar	Smetiprachová *	mayor, deputy chairman of Microregion Nechanicko	Stěžery	5/27/2021
Pavel	Mrkvička	mayor	Třesovice	5/27/2021
Jan	Vratislav	public, former agronomist	Mžany	6/3/2021
Václav	Pražák	public, historian	Nechanice	6/3/2021
Květoslav	Kvasnička	mayor	Kunčice	7/2/2021
Milan	Bartoň	mayor	Lodín	8/5/2021
Miroslava	Kdoulová	mayor	Sověstice	8/9/2021
František	Petřík	mayor	Dohalice	8/17/2021
Václav	Zubr	mayor	Pšánky	8/17/2021
Josef	Pavlíček	mayor	Puchlovice	8/17/2021
Tomáš	Nechvíle	agronomist ZS Kratonohy	Kratonohy	8/17/2021
Tomáš	Valena	mayor	Mžany	9/13/2021
Jiří	Pechar	mayor	Nechanice	9/13/2021
Miloň	Hypius *	private farmer, hunter	Horní Černůtky	9/13/2021
Vít	Barborka	member of the board of municipality	Radíkovice	9/20/2021
Petr	Jahelka	hunter, Hvězda - Mžany	Dohalice	9/20/2021
Jiří	Sooky *	Department of Construction and Environment, city of Nechanice	Nechanice	10/7/2021
Josef	Vyčítal	director of agriculture company ZD Nechanice, hunter	Nechanice	10/7/2021
Aleš	Hypius	public, hunter, former agronomist	Pšánky	10/7/2021
Dušan	Kresl	private farmer in Hřibsko	Stěžery	10/7/2021
Zdeněk	Líznr *	public, hunter	Horní Přím	10/7/2021
Alexandr	Hrabálek	mayor of Hradec Králové, club Neroš	Hradec Králové, Nerošov	12/10/2021
Radomír	Machan	chairman of club Neroš	Hradec Králové, Nerošov	12/10/2021
Jindřich	Prouzek	agronomist ZD Libčany	Libčany	12/10/2021
Jana	Rejlová	director of local action group (MAS) Hradecký venkov	Nechanice	12/10/2021
Milan	Vlk	fisherman	Nechanice	12/10/2021
Petr	Vašátko	private farmer	Nechanice	12/16/2021
Pavel	Novák	public, nature conservationist	Nechanice	1/12/2022
Zdeněk	Unčovský	AOPK - expert organisation of MoE	Pardubice	1/12/2022
Marcela	Hausvaterová	AOPK - expert organisation of MoE	Pardubice	1/12/2022
Karel	Novák	director of agriculture company AGROSEM Stěžery, hunter	Stěžery	2/3/2022
David	Číp	chairman of nature conservation NGO JARO Jaroměř	Jaroměř	3/25/2022
Roman	Rozínek *	nature conservation - executive of NaturaServis s.r.o.	Hradec Králové	4/5/2022
Michal	Vávra	Povodí Labe - management of the	Hradec Králové	6/14/2022

		Elbe basin		
Martin	Trávníček	director of biodiversity conservation NGO Pestré Polabí	Nechanice	6/20/2022
* We met with some stakeholders several times during the duration of the project.				

Table 2 List of meetings in Nechanicko microregion

2.6. Study trips, training, consultancy

Both pilot regions

Regular meetings - We consulted at 13 online meetings with DVL and another 15 online internal meetings (CSO and Ekotoxa). At these meetings, we shared news, set up next goals and discussed new ideas or obstacles. All meetings were summarized in minutes and shared among all project partners.

Internal workshop with DVL - 19.4.2021 (Liselotte Unseld, Beate Krettinger). We went through various topics and questions prepared by the Czech partners. We widely discussed our strategy and got a wider picture of how LPVs in Germany work.

Internal workshop with RILOG - 14.5.2021 Hana Skokanová from The Silva Tarouca Research Institute for Landscape and Ornamental Gardening (RILOG) gave a lecture about their project called MaGICLandscape that took part in the South Moravian region. We discussed communication with stakeholders, obstacles and ways to deal with different situations. She also supported the preparation of Ekotoxa's region map database, which now includes various layers (historical map of the landscape, maps of natural characteristics, water bodies etc.)

Study trips of DVL to the Czech Republic. The first study trip took place only in Nechanice in November 2021, since the seminar in Hrušovansko was cancelled due to an illness of Ekotoxa staff. It was the first time that people from different stakeholder groups met at one event, and at the same time, we were visited by partners from DVL from Germany. The first day started with a public seminar, where local farmers presented responsible care of an agricultural landscape. The microregion and its activities were presented by the mayor of Mokrovousy, Jana Pečenková, who has been helping all 20 municipalities of the microregion for a long time with the implementation of plantings and the renewal of field roads. The CSO presented the first proposals for landscape features that came up during the round table meetings, and some of them will be implemented in the microregion. The following day there was a field trip to 5 locations, which were presented in the form of proposals the previous evening. We stopped together at the straightened bed of the Bystřice river. CSO presented a proposal for a dry polder in Dohalice, which also has the potential to serve to improve the quality of life of local residents and support some animal species. The mayor of Mžany presented, as part of the joint activities of the microregion, the planting near Lubno, which the local hunting association carried out.

The second study trip of DVL leads to the Southern Moravian region in the beginning of April 2022. Two experts from DVL presented at a seminar where stakeholders and the public of the project microregion were invited. We have discussed the possibilities of adapting the landscape with the inspiration of best practice examples of cooperation in German LPVs. The next day we organised an excursion for the project partners, including CSO and DVL to the problematic localities of the microregion.

The study trip to Germany took place between 26th and 28th April 2022. The excursion was intended for project partners from the Czech Republic (Ekotoxa and ČSO) and for stakeholders from project microregions. A total of 14 stakeholders from the Czech Republic took part in the excursion, including representatives of municipalities, nature conservation, farmers, gamekeepers and beekeepers.

On the first day of the trip, project partners and stakeholders from Czechia boarded a rented minibus which drove us to Saxony, the whole journey in Germany and back to Czechia. We made trips by bus, foot and boat to see best practice examples of landscape care carried out by LPVs. In Kirschallee, we were

introduced to involving volunteers in the restoration of the old cherry alley by planting new trees.

Figure 13 Impressions from the study trip to Saxony (V. Chvátalová & V. Zámečník)

During going down to the river Nisa on rafts, the participants learned about the modifications of the banks for the Northern Bear Spider and learned how to protect the riparian vegetation against beaver browsing. We visited valuable habitats presented to us by DVL members and learned further about the organisation and work of DVL and LPVs in the lectures in the evening. The whole trip served very well also as an informal networking opportunity for people from diverse backgrounds who shared an interest in natural values.

2.7. PR activities and publications

Both pilot regions

[Informative leaflet](#) - informative leaflet that presents the project goals, microregions and individual partners.

[Letter of invitation for seminars](#) - press release on CSO website, including the letter of invitation for November seminars in Hrušovany pod Jevišovkou and Nechanice.

[Seminar in Nechanice](#) - the article on the CSO website presents a two-day seminar in Nechanicko. Readers can download the presenters' presentations and view photos from the field trips that featured the locations of the landscape feature designs.

[Excursion to Saxony](#) - report from the study trip about conservation projects in Saxony led by LPV, supplemented by several photos from the participants and their impressions of the trip.

[Leaflet of financial database](#) - card flyer with a website (QR code) about financial database Živá půda ("Living land"). See the related tweet about the database [here](#).

All published materials of the project are integrated into the webpage of the CSO ([link](#)).

Ekotoxa website

[Website of the project](#) - presenting the project area of Hrušovansko, cooperation with the German DVL, information about financing by DBU and activities within the project. Website visitors can also view the Guide for Landowners and Farmers on the website of a related organisation the Partnership Foundation.

CSO website

[Website of the project](#) - introduction of the project and project partners

[Dog Walking with respect to nature](#) - disturbing wildlife is a growing issue, especially in terms of farmland birds nesting on the ground. This article aims to raise awareness among dog walkers and offers 10 tips on how to behave responsibly in nature. Shared also on CSO social media ([Facebook](#) and [Twitter](#)).

Regional press

[Creating healthy landscape](#) - article introducing the project in a regional press Zpravodaj Nechanicko 2/2021.

[Let's respect nature](#) - a short article aiming to raise awareness about disturbing wildlife by dog walking without a leash in wildlife baby season. It was published in a regional press Zpravodaj Nechanicko 2/2021.

[Cooperation of nature conservationists, municipalities and farmers](#) - article in a regional press Zpravodaj Nechanicko 4/2021 about the results of the ornithological survey in Nechanicko region and proposals of landscape features

[Residents of Nechanice on rafts observing Arctosa cinerea and other endangered species](#) - article about the study trip to Saxony published in regional press Zpravodaj Nechanicko 3/2021

3 Problems and obstacles

Both pilot regions

The period of the project. Fifteen months was rather a brief period to establish firm trust and cooperation with stakeholders and to realise landscape features which were proposed in the meetings with stakeholders.

Time requirements for creating landscape features. Various interesting and meaningful ideas about creating/revitalising landscape elements emerged from the individual meetings. The problem is that even a smaller project requires a lot of preparatory work in terms of documentation and communication. Seasonality also plays a crucial role. Due to the interest in cooperation from the side of stakeholders of some municipalities, we see an immense potential in the follow-up project that could provide enough time to realise some of the landscape features.

Pilot region Southern Moravia

The low level of trust (see also chapter 2.2). The development of trust is a long-term process beyond the time scale of this project. It is important that the stakeholders believe in a continuation of the activities started during the project after its end. Therefore, we assured them that we would like to continue our activities in the microregions in the frame of further projects to which we were applying for.

CAP transition period. It was impossible to enter titles supporting agro-environment-climate measures (AECM) and the national strategic plan of CAP has not been authorised yet, so that conditions and titles for the new term 2023-2027 were not clear yet. However, we provided at least information of the currently known proposals of financial mechanisms in the new term and the development of the CAP to require more non-productive activities. Despite that, the majority of approached farmers were not interested in consultations or attending round tables.

Low response from farmers (see also chapter 2.2). Although we tried to repeatedly reach farmers by phone and email during their off-season, we got only a few positive responses that allowed short telephone interviews and a few personal meetings and participation at the round tables. We tailored our approach based on our previous work experience and recommendations resulting from a typology of farmers we created in qualitative research of farmers' motivations to implement adaptations on the landscape level (Meierová and Chvátalová, 2022). That means we tried to capture their interest by offering help with issues worrying them most and possible to be addressed at least partly through cooperation in this project. We offered to help them tackle drought and changing rainfall distribution, wind and water erosion, maintain and improve long-term fertility, provide information on the new CAP and increasing requirements for non-productive functions, advise with subsidies, all with regard to the economic functioning of the company. However, usually they declined arguing that they already have their own advisors or that they are not interested in tackling these issues. Some of them who were invited to the round tables as the users and/or landowners of problematic field blocks, refused to be part of landscape improving efforts as their aim was to produce and be economically stable.

Low interest from representatives of municipalities. Although we have succeeded in meeting all mayors and/or vice mayors of the microregional villages personally or conduct telephone interviews with them in the beginning of the project, their further involvement was limited.

In total, four mayors and one vice mayor attended round tables in four municipalities. The involvement in two villages was successful. However, two mayors agreed with the organisation of a round table in their villages but then did not contribute constructively into the discussion and follow up communication. Representatives of other villages were not interested in the possibility of a round table or had foreseen it for a later date which was out of the period of this project.

Furthermore, none participated in the seminar of DVL nor the excursion to Germany. Although we attempted to make these activities as accessible as possible, the usual response given for not

participating was that it collided with their commitments. Although that may be a true reason, based on the experience and information from other stakeholders, we suspect that some of the representatives are satisfied with the current situation (power relations in the village) and others do not perceive a value in joining the project. One mayor confirmed that by openly saying that he would like to wait and see what the involvement brings to other mayors. Therefore, this obstacle also offers hope for future involvement of some hesitant stakeholders, once they perceive a value based on good experience of their peers.

Financial factors (see also chapter 2.2). The stakeholders potentially interested in creating some landscape features are afraid of the costs for the follow-up measures (mainly the watering of trees which is needed in the dry region beyond the time covered by subsidy projects).

Pilot region Hradec Kralove

Lack of time and money to create landscape features. Mayors in the microregion often face a lack of time to create landscape features or new communication structures with local stakeholders. Mayors from municipalities with fewer inhabitants often have another (full-time) job. Some mayors also mentioned problems with applying for subsidies. However, subsidies can be applied through LAG Hradecký venkov, but EU subsidies for municipalities with a smaller number of employees are bureaucratically very demanding. Most municipalities do not have the means to purchase new land where they could implement landscape elements.

Destruction of new plantings in the agricultural landscape. Mayors mentioned very often the problem of communication with local agricultural cooperatives and subsequent care in the case of the creation of landscape features. In addition, they often stated that farmers disagree with planting in the agricultural landscape and trees planted near the field are destroyed by agricultural machinery. There is also the destruction of bio belts by people who use them as a path. Property rights also stand in the way when creating new landscape features because the new owners who inherited the land often no longer have such a relationship with it, so they are often disinterested in these things.

Threatening natural values. Activities threatening the quality of natural and landscape values in the region are the expansion of the size of the municipalities and the merging of the villages. (see also in chapter 2.2.2) Parts of the area are at risk of floods, insufficient retention or erosion. Locally, during heavy rains, water levels in watercourses and water from large areas of arable land may increase. Beekeepers often complain about the use of herbicides, which leads to bee colonies' health problems.

The construction of the highway and housing. Some cadastres of the region are located at the construction sites of the new D11 motorway. As a result of the Hradec agglomeration and the increasing number of inhabitants, municipalities often face the lack of public amenities for newly immigrated residents. This is related to the pressure of developers on municipalities when the area is rapidly being built up, the result of which is the permanent loss of land and thus the destruction of its production and ecosystem functions.

Residents' lack of interest to get involved in community life and low level of trust. The mayors also perceive insufficient involvement of the young generation in associations such as hunting. (see also chapter 2.2.2)

In the Nechanicko microregion, we could also observe the locals' low level of trust towards introducing new approaches. The mayors do not believe that it is possible to apply all of the methods of LPV. They claim that the main obstacle here is a different socio-economic environment compared to Germany. However, most of the interviewed stakeholders perceived the whole project very positively. Some were actively interested in how to get involved in the project. The project was perceived positively by mayors and associations, who are already engaged in improving the environment and often have already implemented some landscape features themselves.

4 Consolidation and further or connected activities

Both pilot regions

We have succeeded to initiate cooperation where it had not been in place before in both pilot regions. However, as described above, mainly due to the short time frame and social barriers, a formal cooperation structure similar to LPV could not be established yet. Therefore, we would like to continue in developing formal and informal cooperation with mayors, farmers, environmentalists and local clubs, and attract further stakeholders in order to create an independent and permanent cooperation structure in both microregions.

Therefore, we are currently applying for a project which would help us to support these goals through a variety of activities. One of the main activities of the project is to further develop new landscape features. Before we start the realization of biodiversity research and collection of hydrological and climatic data of the area will be preceded. This information helps us to avoid obstacles which can occur during the realisation. This activity could also improve the trust between stakeholders because it brings them together during preparatory work and also during realisation and further maintenance. Preparatory work includes negotiating with landowners when the local people can help. Landscape features has the educational potential also for local farmers who are struggling with drought or erosion.

Additionally, we will attempt to acquire further funding through other available opportunities. In the meantime, we will stay connected with the most involved stakeholders and support them as part of our usual working tasks when possible. Cooperation with municipalities or LAGs on projects dedicated to a healthy environment is possible here. Some of these project designs have already been included in the strategic plans of the municipalities, and some have even been elaborated in detailed studies.

Pilot region Southern Moravia

Thanks to networking, Friends of the Earth became interested in applying together with Ekotoxa and other subjects for a funding of a project which aims to use a cooperative approach to support adoption of organic farming in a geographically defined region. The project² was acquired and will be implemented between June 2022 and April 2024. Ekotoxa staff will be able to partly continue the activities in Moravian region thanks to this project. We will use the knowledge from this project to prepare and organise meetings for stakeholders in a region that is to be selected based on the potential to transit to organic agriculture.

Pilot region Hradec Králové

Many of the landscape elements proposed by the participants of the round tables are very demanding in terms of money and workforce. To successfully complete proposed landscape features a feasibility study will precede project documentation. The level of consolidation of the built structures and the continuation of the development of landscape elements will depend on how much time investment we will be able to provide to the project in terms of personnel. Our effort is to maintain the highest possible interdependence and continuity between projects. If we do not receive further subsidy, we plan to develop the project on a voluntary basis using local volunteers or engage local municipalities. Basic co-funding may also be offered through the support of the Hradec Králové region or the Ministry of the Environment of the Czech Republic.

We were discussing Operational Programme Employment (OPE) and other co-funding possibilities for landscape features (dedicated to improving water retention) with the Nature Conservation Agency of the Czech Republic (NCA) and with a water management institution such as Povodí Labe.

² Project "Introduction of the bioregion concept as a support network for biodiversity in the Czech landscape: Pilot application of research" under Rago call.

Annex 1 -Article in regional press - Creating a healthy landscape

region

ZA ZDRAVOU KRAJINOU SPOLEČNĚ S ČESKOU SPOLEČNOSTÍ ORNITOLOGICKOU

▪ Nová mez s výsadbou keřů u Lubna. Foto: Václav Zámečník

Polní cesty, stromořadí, meze a mokřady do zdravé krajiny patří a na Nechanicku to není žádná novina. Probíhá zde řada výsadeb a obnovují se historické polní cesty. Také Česká společnost ornitologická se zde podílela na vzniku křovinatých mezí a dlouhodobě usiluje o zachování druhové rozmanitosti v krajinné spolupráci s místními zemědělci. V únoru letošního roku navíc společně s německým spolkem pro péči o krajinu DVL zahájila nový projekt Cesta ke zdravější zemědělské krajinné spolupráci ochránců přírody, samosprávy a zemědělců. Projekt založený na komunikaci představuje příležitost pro každého, kdo chce přispět k vytváření pestřejší a odolnější krajiny. Jak známo, právě vzájemné porozumění je v této věci klíčové. Zástupcům samosprávy, zemědělcům, vlastníkům půdy a ochráncům přírody se tak otevírá možnost společně projednat své představy a možná úskalí u kulatých stolů. Velmi vítané je zapojení mysliveckých sdružení, rybářů, včelařů nebo také jednotlivců se zájmem o přírodu.

ČSO chce v rámci projektu podpo-

rovat vedle vhodných výsadeb také revitalizaci odvodněných ploch a vytváření mokřadů v krajině. Vlastníkům půdy a zemědělcům rozhodnutým hospodařit šetrnějším způsobem může navíc pomoci při získávání potřebných informací ohledně finanční podpory z programů Ministerstva zemědělství

nebo Ministerstva životního prostředí.

Není náhodou, že zemědělský specialista ČSO Václav Zámečník vybral jako projektové území právě mikroregion. Nechanicko je především místo, kde sám žije a je přirozenou snahou každého udělat si prostředí kolem sebe hezké. I proto projekt vznikl, uvedl.

A přirozenou snahou každého ornitologa je pohlížet na plánované úpravy v krajině z ptáčích perspektiv. Pestré prostředí je naprosto zásadní pro přežití řady ohrožených druhů zemědělské krajiny. Jejich dramatický úbytek způsobuje intenzivní zemědělství a vše, co s ním souvisí – rychlá mechanizace, chemizace, odvodňování mokřadních lokalit a scelování pozemků. Navíc právě nyní, při jarních přípravách půdy, hrozí ptákům přímé nebezpečí v podobě zemědělských strojů, které ničím nechráněná hnízda likvidují. Na Nechanicku se dosud udržely ohrožené čejky chocholaté, vzácné koroptve polní, tuňáci obecní i šedí. Hnízdí zde až tři páry čápů bi-

lých i čápi černí, kteří na louky a pole zaletují za potravou. Stále častěji lze pozorovat motáky lužní, orly mořské, volavky bílé, strnady luční nebo husice mlíské. Pravidelně se začínají objevovat i jeřábi popelaví. Snahou ČSO je pomoci nejen těmto, ale i řadě dalších druhů, k nalezení útočiště a hnízdních příležitostí.

Aktivita ČSO v mikroregionu Nechanicko podpořila Německá spolková nadace pro životní prostředí DBU a Královéhradecký kraj. Nejzapálenější účastníci čeká kromě užší spolupráce i exkurze do Německa, kde se model ochrany přírody založené na spolupráci ochránců přírody, samosprávy a zemědělců úspěšně rozvíjí.

V případě zájmu nebo možnosti sdílet užitečné poznatky o mikroregionu se neváhejte spojit s pracovníky ČSO:

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▪ Koroptev polní. Foto: Bohuslav Pešek

BUĎME OHLEDUPLNÍ K PŘÍRODĚ

V posledních letech se stále častěji mluví o zemědělské krajině a jejích problémech se suchem, erozí chemizací, ztrátou krajinných prvků nebo druhové pestrosti. Cesta ke zlepšení stavu krajiny je dlouhodobý proces často podmíněný politickými rozhodnutími, ale přispět tomu, aby příroda v našem okolí vzkvétala, může každý jednotlivec. Zatímco působení na politickém poli není pro každého, stále existuje řada problémů, za které neseme zodpovědnost jen my, a nikdo jiný. Jedním z nich je rušení divokých zvířat volně pobíhajícími psy, ke kterému v dnešní hustě osídlené krajině dochází příliš často. Dopládá na to široká škála živočichů, nejčastěji srnky, zajáci a ptáci.

Česká společnost ornitologická by touto cestou chtěla poprosit pejskaře, aby měli své psy při procházkách krajinou pod kontrolou. Společně s kynoložkou ČSO Klárou Hlubockou vytvořila seznam tipů pro všechny majitele psů, kteří kolem sebe při svých procházkách nechtějí působit zbytečnou škodu:

Dodržujeme zákazy a respektujeme omezení vstupu se psy nebo se psy pobíhajícími na volno.

Vnímáme krajinu a život v ní. Respektujeme fakt, že nejsme jediní, kdo zde potřebuje prostor pro život. Sledujeme, které druhy žijí v okolí našeho

domova, kdy a kde se pohybují, jestli mají mláďata. Pokud tudy procházíme, dejme svého psa na vodítko.

Mějme své psy stále pod kontrolou. Pouštějme je jen tam, kde máme o jejich pohybu přehled. Držme si je na vzdálenost max. 20 - 30 metrů od sebe (pokud se při venčení bavíme s někým jiným, či telefonujeme, psi toho neuvěřitelně rychle využijí).

Přivolání a zastavení je základ. Navíc pozor, co psa naučíme doma, nemusí fungovat venku. Než svého psa pustíme venku z vodítka, mějme dobře natrénovaný a upevněný povel pro přivolání nebo zastavení (tzn., že pes poslechne, i když vyruší nějaké zvíře, které před ním začne utíkat). Pokud tohle pes neumí, venčeme ve volné přírodě pouze na tzv. flexi vodítku, nebo na dlouhé šňůře, kterou máme možnost kdykoliv psa zastavit.

Předvídejme a naučme se psa dostat pod kontrolu dřív, než vyběhne.

Zaměstnaná hlava = hodný pes. Věnujme se svému psu, pro udržení jeho pozornosti. Procházkou nepravidelně zpestřujeme občasnou duševní činností. Ať už je to hledání hraček nebo pánčkových předmětů (pamlsky nedoporučujeme, protože jejich sbírání venku může být rizikové), cvičení triků nebo cviků poslušnosti. Pokud psu činnost nenabídneme, najde si ji zpravidla sám

a nebývá to většinou to, co by se nám zrovna líbilo.

Tento text vznikl v rámci projektu *Cesta ke zdravější zemědělské krajině*

spoluprací ochránců přírody, samospráv a zemědělců podpořený Německou spolkovou nadací pro životní prostředí DBU.
Karolína Mikšlová

■ Výsadba u Lubna. Foto: Karolína Mikšlová

Annex 3 - Article in regional press - Cooperation of nature conservationists, municipalities and farmer

region

SPOLUPRÁCE OCHRÁNCŮ PŘÍRODY, SAMOSPRÁVY A ZEMĚDĚLCŮ

Nechanicko - V jarním čísle Zpravodaje mikroregionu (2/2021) jsme představili projekt České společnosti ornitologické (ČSO) s názvem Cesta ke zdravější zemědělské krajině spoluprací ochránců přírody, samosprávy a zemědělců. Od zahájení projektu uplynulo přes osm měsíců a my za sebou máme řadu individuálních schůzek a dní v terénu. Bavíme se o krajině, zemědělství a možnostech, jak na území Nechanicka vytvořit více prostoru pro přírodu. Na povrch postupně vychází jeden návrh k oživení krajiny za druhým. Za spolupráci a četné nápady vdčíme jak zúčastněným stranám v názvu projektu, tak mysliveckým sdružením nebo obyvatelům mikroregionu.

Zkrátka nepřichází ani naše nejoblíbenější zúčastněná strana projektu – ptáci. Polní druhy ptáků na území Nechanicka zmapovali ornitologové Lukáš Kadava a Oldřich Forman. Celkem zaznamenali přes 60 druhů více či méně vázaných na zemědělskou krajinu. Z nejčastějších pozorování můžeme jmenovat například tuňhýka obecného, strnada obecného, skřivana polního, motáka pochopa nebo vlaštovku obecnou. Žalostně málo záznamů pak bylo

zjištěno o dříve běžných druzích, jako je koroptev polní nebo hrdlička divoká. Ptáci zemědělské krajiny doplácí na nedostatek pestrosti v krajině i na Nechanicku a malé zastoupení zmíněných druhů jsou toho důkazem. Potýkají se zde také s nedostatkem vody v krajině, což se týká především skupiny bahňáček, kam patří čejka chocholátka nebo kulík říční. Právě na velká hejna čejek a racků chechtavých vzpomínali lidé na nejednom z našich společných setkání.

Schůzky a výjezdy do terénu ale nejsou všechno. Nejvíce času trávíme, jako dnes už snad každý, za počítačem. Poznatky z terénu a vybrané návrhy na oživení krajiny shromažďujeme a zpracováváme do většího detailu k dalšímu projednávání. Kromě toho vzniká ve spolupráci s nadací Partnerství přehledná a uživatelsky velmi přátelská databáze dotací, která bude zpřístupněna na webu Živé půdy během podzimu. Kdokoliv se zájmem udělat něco pro krajinu bude mít brzy možnost se rychle a bezbolestně dopátrat toho pravého dotačního programu pro svůj zájem. To ocení určitě každý, kdo se už ve spleť světě dotací někdy ocitl.

K ozdravení krajiny můžeme dojít

různými způsoby. My si vybrali cestu založenou na vzájemné komunikaci a hledání společného východiska. I v příštích měsících nás proto čekají hlavně různorodá setkání, pořádání kulatých stolů a zajímavé diskuze o krajině, které navážou na podzimní seminář pořádaný první týden v listopadu. Chcete-li být součástí projektu, neváhejte se nám ozvat se svými podněty. Třeba se právě váš nápad podaří

v budoucnu zrealizovat a krajina Nechanicka bude zase o něco pestřejší.

Aktivity ČSO v mikroregionu Nechanicko podporuje Německá spolková nadace pro životní prostředí DBU a Královéhradecký kraj.

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- Projekt by mohl přispět k obnovení polní cesty vedoucí z Pšánek do Nerošova. Foto: Václav Zámečník

Annex 4 - Article in regional press - Residents of Nechanice on rafts observing *Arctosa cinerea* and other endangered species

region

NECHANICHTÍ VYRAZILI NA RAFTECH ZA SLÍDÁKEM BŘEHOVÝM A DALŠÍMI OHROŽENÝMI DRUHY

Na počátku roku 2021 zahájila Česká společnost ornitologická (ČSO) ve spolupráci se společností Ekotoxa a německým spolkem pro péči o krajinu DVL (Deutscher Verband für Landschaftspflege) projekt Cesta ke zdravější zemědělské krajině spoluprací ochránců přírody, samospráv a zemědělců. Čtenáři zpravodaje se mohli s projektem seznámit již v předchozích číslech 2/2021 a 4/2021. Z názvu projektu lze odvodit také jeho hlavní cíl – vytvoření trvalé spolupráce mezi jednotlivými zájmovými skupinami, které se podílejí na utváření zemědělské krajiny. V listopadu minulého roku proběhl v Nechanicích seminář, kde kolegové z DVL představili ve svých prezentacích aktivitu spojené s ochranou přírody. Protože by byla škoda si tyto projekty ukazovat pouze na fotografiích, rozhodli jsme se na konci dubna 2022 uspořádat exkurzi přímo do Saska, abychom si ochránářské úspěchy DVL mohli prohlédnout pěkně zblízka. Někteří účastníci byli natolik nadšení, že se rozhodli nenechat si své dojmy z exkurze pro sebe a podělit se o ně s Vámi.

„Naše první zastávka byla Kirschallee, kde o více jak 85 let starou třeš-

ňovou alej pečuje Spolek pro ochranu krajiny Horní Lužice. Alej je potřeba udržovat dosazováním nových stromů. Právě zde spatřuje LPV potenciál ke spolupráci s veřejností. Na nové stromy přispěli dárci, přičemž někteří si je také sami zasadili. Každý vysazený strom byl opatřen cedulkou se jménem darce. Následovala procházka kolem rekultivovaného hnědouhelného dolu Berzdorfer See, který dnes slouží především jako místo k rekreaci.

Další den nás čekal sjezd řeky Nisy na raftech. Udělali jsme si zastávku na písčitém břehu, který je udržován proti zarůstáním vegetací, aby na něm mohl žít vzácný druh pavouka slíďák břehový (*Arctosa cinerea*). Odpoledne jsme se přemístili do Lodenau, kde jsme si prohlédli vodní tok obsazený bobrem evropským. Němečtí kolegové nám zde ukázali, jak je možné zabezpečit vysazované keře a stromy před okusem tohoto chráněného druhu, který se sem navrátil z polské strany. Během naší cesty jsme se navštívili také několik míst, kde vznikly v rámci aktivit na podporu přírody hmyzí hotely, budky pro ptáky a různé ekovychovné prvky pro děti i dospělé.

Třetí den naší výpravy jsme navštívili unikátní hřbitov, ve kterém roste 1700 lip pravidelně ořezávaných tzv. „na hlavu“. V Olbersdorfu jsme si prohlédli mokřady, které slouží k napájení koupaliště, ochráně před povodněmi zároveň a jako prostor pro rozmnožování obojživelníků. Naši poslední zastávkou byl Waltersdorf, kde nám LPV prezentovalo projekty na záchranu tamních ohrožených druhů. Naši průvodci nám předali mnoho informací o tom, jak v této části Německa pečují o krajinu, jaké úsilí musí vynaložit pro získání finanční podpory a jak je potřeba změnit myšlení lidí, aby pochopili, co je důležité proto, abychom mohli žít na této planetě v souladu s přírodními zákony. Výsledkem našeho ochránářského putování po Sasku bylo především poznání, že když se spojí lidé různých profesí a zájmů (zemědělci, ornitologové, včelaři, ochránci přírody, členové místních samospráv a další) kterým není lhostejný stav přírody, diskutují spolu a hledají kompromisy, tak mohou najít společnou cestu a mnohé změnit.“ Radim Kupka a Ivana Šabaková.

Exkurze do Saska není zdaleka poslední akce, kterou v rámci projektu

plánujeme. Na podzim nás čekají další setkání v rámci kulatých stolů, na kterých se s rádi kromě zástupců samospráv, zemědělců a místními spolky potkáme také s širokou veřejností. Zemědělská krajina Nechanicka se bohužel stále více potýká s problémem sucha, což se projevuje také při diskuzích s místními obyvateli. Z proběhlých kulatých stolů vyplynulo, že nedostatek vody v krajině vnímali účastníci jako jeden z největších problémů na Nechanicku vůbec. Není tak překvapivé, že více jak polovina navržených podnětů občany se věnovala právě vodě. Někteří v současnosti opomíjená místa mají velký potenciál pro řešení sucha i podpory biodiverzity minimálně na lokální úrovni. Na podzim letošního roku bychom rádi představili výsledky našich jednání s Povodím Labe a návrh na revitalizaci mokřadu v Komárově v Nechanicích zpracovaný firmou NaturaServis s. r. o.

Aktivitu projektu byly podpořeny Německou spolkovou nadací pro životní prostředí DBU a Královéhradeckým krajem.

Václav Zámečnick, Michaela Kadavá

▪ Stará třešňová alej v Saském Kirschallee. Foto: Veronika Chvátalová

▪ Účastníci exkurze obdivují velký hmyzí hotel. Foto: Ivana Šabaková

▪ Vyjíždka na raftech po řece Nise. Foto: Václav Zámečnick

Cesta ke zdravější zemědělské krajině spoluprací ochránců přírody, samosprávy a zemědělců

O projektu

Česko-německý projekt České společnosti ornitologické, společnosti Ekotoxa a německého spolku pro péči o krajinu DVL je podpořený Německou spolkovou nadací pro životní prostředí DBU. Hlavním cílem projektu je vytvoření prostoru pro vzájemnou diskuzi mezi samosprávou, vlastníky pozemků, zemědělci a ochránci přírody a nalezení společné cesty k pestřejší a stabilnější zemědělské krajině. Plánujeme propojovat všechny uvedené zájmové skupiny i veřejnost a motivovat je k vytváření zdravé zemědělské krajiny v projektových územích. Během individuálních setkání a společných kulatých stolů představíme odborným průzkumem podložené návrhy na zlepšení stavu vybraných ploch včetně možností jejich financování a budeme společně hledat způsob, jak návrhy uskutečnit.

Příklad spolupráce německého spolku pro krajinu

Ochránci přírody, zemědělci a starostové se spojili ve Würzberském spolku pro péči o krajinu, když tam byla část intenzivně obdělávaná zemědělská oblast vyhlášena jako ptačí rezervace. Cílem spolku je označovat hnízda ptáků hnízdicích na zemi, vytvářet meze, remízky a shodnout se se zemědělci na opatřeních jako vytváření biopásů, ponechání pásu plodin a extenzivní využití částí půdy. Za to spolek pomáhá zemědělcům získávat finanční kompenzace.

foto: Deutscher Verband für Landschaftspflege

Zapojte se

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Cesta ke zdravější zemědělské krajině

spoluprací ochránců přírody, samosprávy a zemědělců

Projektová území

Nechanicko

V nížinné oblasti Nechanicka se rozkládají zejména zemědělsky využívané plochy s menším podílem lesa. Krajina je významně pozměněná přechodem od tradičního soukromého zemědělství na velkoplošné hospodaření. Dnes zde dominují velké půdní bloky s nedostatkem krajinných prvků. ČSO zde navazuje na mapování hnízd čejek chocholatých a další aktivity spojené s ochranou biodiverzity.

Hrušovansko

Hrušovansko je rovinaté území s převažujícím intenzivním hospodařením a s vysokým zastoupením velkých dílů půdních bloků. S malým podílem krajinnotvorných prvků v lokalitě se pojí negativní jevy, jako je nízká biodiverzita, eroze, nedostatečná zádrž vody v půdě či snížená propustnost krajiny. Chybějící krajinná mozaika má také nepříznivý dopad na krajinný ráz oblasti. Ekotoxa navazuje na územní studii krajiny, kterou zpracovala pro Znojensko.

Partneři

ČSO zkoumá a chrání ptáky, jejich prostředí a přírodu jako celek a svou činností k tomu motivuje i širokou veřejnost. Od roku 2003 se věnuje ochraně zemědělské krajiny.

EKOTOXA je poradenská, analytická a projekční společnost věnující se oblastem životního prostředí, zemědělství, lesnictví a rozvoje území.

DVL působí v Německu jako zastřešující organizace sdružující zástupce zemědělství a lesnictví, ochrany přírody a obcí s cílem rozvíjet rozmanitou a udržitelnou krajinu.

foto: Bohuslav Pešek

Annex 6 - leaflet Database Živá půda

Chcete pomoci zlepšit stav české půdy a krajiny?
Ale chybí vám na to finance?

Finanční podporu na různé typy opatření najdete na:
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